

THE DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF A NOVEL RP-HPLC METHOD FOR THE SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF ABIRATERONE AND NIRAPARIB IN BULK AND PHARMACEUTICAL DOSAGE FORMULATIONS

Sajeeda Begum, P. Divya, P. Sridevi, Archana Awasthi*

Department of Pharmaceutical Analysis, Sri Venkateshwara College of Pharmacy,
Madhapur, Hyderabad-500081, Telangana, India.

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*Corresponding Author

Archana Awasthi

Department of Pharmaceutical
Analysis, Sri Venkateshwara College
of Pharmacy, Madhapur, Hyderabad-
500081, Telangana, India.

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ABSTRACT

A simple, precise, and robust RP-HPLC method was developed for the simultaneous estimation of Abiraterone (ABNE) and Niraparib (NIPB) using an Altima C18 column (150 × 4.6 mm, 5 μm). Chromatographic separation was achieved with a mobile phase consisting of 0.1% OPA and acetonitrile in a 55:45 (v/v) ratio, delivered at a flow rate of 1 mL/min. Detection was carried out at 234 nm. The retention times of ABNE and NIPB were 2.350 min and 3.044 min, respectively. System suitability parameters were within acceptable limits, with %RSD values of 0.2% for ABNE and 0.8% for NIPB. The method demonstrated excellent accuracy, with recovery values of 99.21% for ABNE and 100.92% for NIPB. Linearity was established with regression equations of $y = 36905x + 108959$ for ABNE and $y = 49978x + 5769$ for NIPB. Overall, the developed method is suitable for routine quality control analysis of ABNE and NIPB in pharmaceutical formulations.

KEYWORDS: ABNE, NIPB, RP-HPLC.

INTRODUCTION

High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) has emerged as one of the most essential and reliable techniques in pharmaceutical analysis, particularly for the separation and

quantification of active pharmaceutical ingredients.^[1] Reverse-phase HPLC (RP-HPLC) is the most widely used chromatographic technique in pharmaceutical analysis due to its excellent resolution and broad applicability to diverse drug molecules. Its use of stable aqueous–organic mobile phases enhance method reproducibility and ensures consistent analytical performance. RP-HPLC also delivers superior peak symmetry and high sensitivity, enabling accurate quantification even at low analyte concentrations. The method is highly robust, maintaining reliability despite minor variations in pH, temperature, or mobile phase composition. Because of its versatility and effectiveness with complex mixtures, RP-HPLC remains a preferred choice for routine quality control and multi-component drug analysis.^[2]

Antineoplastic agents play a critical role in the treatment of various malignancies by inhibiting or preventing the proliferation of cancerous cells.^[3] Given the therapeutic importance of these agents, precise and accurate analytical methods are required to ensure their quality, efficacy, and safety. Developing validated analytical methods is crucial to comply with regulatory standards and to facilitate routine quality control during pharmaceutical manufacturing.^[4]

The present study focuses on the development and validation of a novel RP-HPLC method for the simultaneous estimation of abiraterone and niraparib in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage formulations.

Abiraterone is an oral medication primarily used in the treatment of prostate cancer particularly metastatic castration-resistant prostate cancer (mCRPC) and metastatic high-risk castration-sensitive prostate cancer (mCSPC).^[5]

It works by inhibiting cytochrome P450 17A1 (CYP17A1), an enzyme involved in the production of androgens (male hormones like testosterone) that fuel the growth of prostate cancer cells. Initially developed as a treatment for breast cancer, its greater potential was later recognized in prostate cancer due to the androgen-dependency of the disease.

Abiraterone is indicated in combination with prednisone for the treatment of metastatic high-risk castration-sensitive prostate cancer (CSPC). In Europe and Canada, it may also be used in combination with prednisolone and androgen deprivation therapy in newly diagnosed patients.^[6]

Niraparib is an oral PARP (Poly ADP-Ribose Polymerase) inhibitor used primarily in the treatment of ovarian cancer.^[7] It belongs to a class of targeted cancer therapies designed to exploit specific genetic weaknesses in cancer cells, especially those involving defects in DNA repair pathways.^[8]

Figure 1: Structures of Abiraterone and Niraparib.

Several studies have focused on developing reliable analytical methods for abiraterone and niraparib using RP-HPLC. A stability-indicating RP-HPLC method was established for the quantitative determination of abiraterone in bulk and dosage forms, achieving clear separation of the drug from its degradation products generated under acidic, basic, oxidative, thermal, and photolytic stress conditions.^[9] Another investigation introduced a new stability-indicating RP-HPLC method capable of simultaneously determining abiraterone acetate, its related impurities, and degradation products in both bulk and formulated products.^[10]

For niraparib, an innovative stability-indicating HPLC method was developed to enable accurate quantification and impurity profiling in pharmaceutical formulations.^[11]

Additionally, a robust RP-HPLC method was designed and validated for the simultaneous estimation of niraparib and abiraterone, demonstrating effective separation of both analytes within an optimized runtime and maintaining specificity in the presence of formulation excipients.^[12,13] Furthermore, a sensitive RP-HPLC/UV method was developed for quantifying abiraterone in rat plasma, featuring efficient extraction and accurate measurement at low concentration levels suitable for pharmacokinetic studies, with all validation parameters meeting regulatory criteria.^[14]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

NIPB and ABNE acetate pure drugs (API) received from spectrum labs, Hyderabad. All chemicals used were of analytical grade. Acetonitrile (MeCN), Water (H₂O), Methanol

(HPLC grade), potassium dihydrogen phosphate (KH_2PO_4), and orthophosphoric acid (OPA) were procured from Merck, India.

INSTRUMENTATION

The instrumentation used in the study included a Waters HPLC 2695 system equipped with Empower 2 software, a Labman sonicator, a Labman pH meter, a Sisco hot air oven, and a Remi vortex mixer.

METHODS

Diluent: Based upon the solubility of the drugs, diluent was selected, Acetonitrile and water taken in the ratio of 50:50.^[15]

Preparation of Standard stock solution: accurately weigh 5 mg of Niraparib, 25mg of Abiraterone and transferred to 25ml and 25ml individual volumetric flasks and 3/4th of diluents was added to these flasks and sonicated for 10 mins. Flasks were made up with diluents and labelled as standard stock solution.^[9]

Preparation of standard working solution (100%): 1ml from each stock solution was pipetted out and taken into a 10ml volumetric flask and make up with diluent.^[16]

Preparation of sample stock solution: 5 tablets were weighed and the average weight of each tablet was calculated, then the weight equivalent to 1 tablet was transferred into a 100ml volumetric flask, 5ml of diluents was added and sonicated for 25 min, further the volume was made up with diluent and filtered by HPLC filters.^[17]

Preparation of sample working solution: 0.2ml of filtered sample stock solution was transferred to 10 ml volumetric flask and made up with diluent.^[17]

Preparation of buffer

0.01N KH_2PO_4 buffer: Accurately weighed 1.36 gm of potassium dihydrogen ortho phosphate in a 1000 ml of volumetric add about 90 ml of milli-Q water added and degas to sonicate and finally make up with water then added 1ml of triethylamine then pH adjusted to 3.8 with dil. Orthophosphoric acid solution.^[18]

Procedure: 6 injections were used to validate the parameters.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

OPTIMIZED METHOD: The chromatographic analysis was carried out using a mobile phase consisting of 55% 0.1% OPA buffer and 45% acetonitrile, delivered at a flow rate of 1 mL/min. Separation was achieved on an Altima C18 column (4.6 × 150 mm, 5 μm) with the detector set at 220 nm and the column maintained at 30 °C. A 10 μL injection volume was used, and the total run time was 6 minutes. The diluent employed for sample preparation was a mixture of water and acetonitrile in a 50:50 ratio (Table 1). Under these conditions, both analytes exhibited well-resolved peaks with acceptable tailing factors, theoretical plate counts, and overall resolution.

Table 1: Optimized Chromatographic conditions.

Mobile phase	55% 0.1% OPA buffer: 45% Acetonitrile
Flow rate	1 ml/min
Column	Altima C18 (4.6 x 150 mm, 5 μm)
Detector wave length	220 nm
Column temperature	30 ⁰ C
Injection volume	10μL
Run time	6min
Diluent	Water and Acetonitrile in the ratio 50:50
Result	Both peaks have good resolution, tailing Factor, theoretical plate count and resolution.

Figure 2. Optimized chromatogram.

Observation: ABNE and NIPB are eluted at 2.350 mints and 3.044 mints respectively with good resolution. Plate count and tailing factor was very satisfactory, so this method was optimized and to be validated (Figure 2).

SYSTEM SUITABILITY: 6 injections were used to validate the parameters as shown in table 2.

Table 2: System suitability parameters for ABNE and NIPB.

ABNE			NIPB			
RT	USP plate count	Tailing Factor	RT (min)	USP plate count	Tailing Factor	Resolution
2.349	5440	1.18	3.036	3642	1.33	4.1
2.349	5441	1.18	3.037	3620	1.33	4.0
2.351	5379	1.19	3.037	3599	1.33	4.1
2.352	5388	1.15	3.037	3555	1.33	4.0
2.353	5440	1.15	3.038	3656	1.31	4.1
2.354	5483	1.15	3.041	3556	1.33	4.1

Figure 3. System suitability Chromatogram.

DISCUSSION

all the system suitable parameters were passed and were within limits (Figure 3).

METHOD VALIDATION

SPECIFICITY: Checking of the interferences in the optimized method. No interference was found (Figure 4 and 5).

Figure 4. Blank chromatogram.

Figure 5. Placebo chromatogram.

LINEARITY: The standard solutions were developed as follows:

Preparation

Linearity 25%: 0.25ml standard in 10ml volumetric flask then filled with diluent till mark.

Linearity 50%: 0.5ml standard in 10ml volumetric flask then filled with diluent till mark.

Linearity 75%: 0.75ml standard in 10ml volumetric flask then filled with diluent till mark.

Linearity 100%: 1.0 ml standard in 10ml volumetric flask then filled with diluent till mark.

Linearity 125%: 1.25ml standard in 10ml volumetric flask then filled with diluent till mark.

Linearity 150%: 1.50 ml standard in 10ml volumetric flask then filled with diluent till mark.

Six linear concentrations of Abiraterone (25-150 μ g/ml) and Niraparib (5-30 μ g/ml) were injected in a duplicate manner. Average areas were mentioned above and linearity equations obtained (Table 3, Figure 6 and 7).

Table 3: Linearity table for ABNE and NIPB.

ABNE		NIPB	
Conc. (μ g/mL)	Peak area	Conc. (μ g/mL)	Peak area
25	1086797	5	252172
50	2011439	10	496335
75	2923256	15	766360
100	3821209	20	1032858
125	4688235	25	1256279
150	5606991	30	1484053

Figure 6. Calibration plot of ABNE.

Figure 7. Calibration curve of NIPB.

DISCUSSION

6 linear conc of ABNE (25-150 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) and NIPB (5-30 $\mu\text{g/ml}$). linearity equations obtained for ABNE was $y = 36905.x + 108959$ and of NIPB was $y = 49978x + 5769$.

Figure 8. Linearity 25% Chromatogram of Abiraterone and Niraparib.

Figure 9. Linearity 50 % Chromatogram of Abiraterone an Niraparib.

Figure 10. Linearity 75% Chromatogram of Abiraterone and Niraparib.

Figure 11. Linearity 100% Chromatogram of Abiraterone and Niraparib.

Figure 12. Linearity 125% Chromatogram of Abiraterone and Niraparib.

Figure 13. Linearity 150% Chromatogram of Abiraterone and Niraparib.

PRECISION

System Precision: From a single volumetric flask of working standard solution six injections were given and the obtained areas were mentioned Below. Average area, standard deviation and % RSD were calculated for two drugs. By injecting the standard 100% solution into an HPLC precision is achieved (Table 4 and Figure 14).

Table 4: System precision table of ABNE and NIPB.

Area of ABNE	Area of NIPB
3812000	1075635
3836802	1083430
3814192	1072894
3828128	1075204
3824509	1059196
3816659	1067540
3822048	1072317
9512.3	8223.8
0.2	0.8

Figure 14. System precision chromatogram.

DISCUSSION: % RSD obtained as 0.2% and 0.8% respectively for ABNE and NIPB.

Method Precision: Multiple sampling from a sample stock solution was done and six working sample solutions of same concentrations were prepared each injection from each working sample solution was given and obtained areas were mentioned in the below (Table 5 and, Figure 15).

Table 5: Method Precision table of ABNE and NIPB.

S.NO.	Area of ABNE	Area of NIPB
1	3791937	1069360
2	3784051	1054380
3	3793650	1053556
4	3789121	1072550
5	3782331	1058699
6	3792837	1068453
Mean	3788988	1062833
S.D	4773.9	8285.1
%RSD	0.1	0.8

Figure 15. Repeatability chromatogram for ABNE and NIPB.

DISCUSSION: % Relative standard density (RSD) was calculated for both drugs and obtained as 0.1% and 0.8% for ABNE and NIPB respectively.

INTERMEDIATE PRECISION: Illustrated in Table 6 and, Figure 16.

Table 6: Table of intermediate precision of ABNE and NIPB.

S. No	Area of ABNE	Area of NIPB
1.	3929409	1088672
2.	3904203	1095698
3.	3925132	1099574
4.	3914937	1095548
5.	3926559	1097245
6.	3926559	1101211
Mean	3921133	1096325
S.D	9678.7	4355.2
%RSD	0.2	0.4

Figure 16. Inter Day precision Chromatogram for ABNE and NIPB.

DISCUSSION: % RSD was 0.2% and 0.4% respectively for ABNE and NIPB. As the limit of precision was less than 2 the system precision was passed in this method.

ACCURACY: following solutions are prepared.

50% sol: 0.25ml sample sol + 1ml standard solution in 10ml volumetric flask

100% sol: 0.5ml sample sol + 1ml standard solution in 10ml volumetric flask

150% sol: 0.75ml sample sol + 1ml standard solution in 10ml volumetric flask.

Three levels of accuracy samples were prepared by standard addition method. Triplicate injections were given for each level of accuracy and mean %recovery was obtained (Table 7, Figure17, 18 and 19).

Table 7: Accuracy table of ABNE and NIPB.

% Level	ABNE				NIPB			
	Added	Recovered	%Recovery	Avg %	Added	Recovered	%Recovery	Avg %
50%	50	49.5714402	99.14	99.21	10	10.071131	100.71	100.92
		49.3518222	98.70			10.0966825	100.97	
		49.7645847	99.53			10.0439994	100.44	
100%	100	99.1308766	99.13		20	20.1265357	100.63	
		99.1787834	99.18			20.3601585	101.80	
		98.9884027	98.99			20.2592341	101.30	
150%	150	148.770871	99.18		30	30.1396615	100.47	
		149.999106	100.00			30.4880147	101.63	
		148.617613	99.08			30.1007443	100.34	

DISCUSSION: % Recovery was obtained as 99.21% and 100.92% for ABNE and NIPB respectively.

Figure 17. Accuracy 50% Chromatogram of ABNE and NIPB.

Figure 18. Accuracy 100% Chromatogram of ABNE and NIPB.

Figure 19. Accuracy 150% Chromatogram of ABNE and NIPB.

SENSITIVITY: 0.25 ml solution prepared from standard solution in 10ml volumetric flask and LOD and LOQ were prepared (Table 8 and, Figure 20 and 21).

Table 8: Sensitivity data for ABNE and NIPB.

Molecule	LOD	LOQ
Abiraterone	0.01	0.03
Niraparib	0.08	0.23

Figure 20. LOD Chromatogram of Standard ABNE & NIPB.

Figure 21. LOQ Chromatogram of Standard ABNE and NIPB.

ROBUSTNESS: Robustness conditions like Flow minus (0.9 ml/min), Flow plus (1.1ml/min), mobile phase minus (60B:40A), mobile phase plus (50B:50A), temperature minus (25⁰C) and temperature plus (35⁰C) were maintained and samples were injected in duplicate manner (Table 9).

Table 9: Robustness data for ABNE and NIPB.

	RSD ABNE	RSD NIPB
Flow (-) 0.9 ml/min	0.1	0.3
Flow (+) 1.1 ml/min	0.7koix	0.6
Melting Point (-) 60B:40A	0.6	0.3
Melting Point (+) 50B:50A	0.2	0.02
Temperature (-) 25°C	1.2	0.7
Temperature (+) 35°C	0.4	0.2

Discussion: System suitability parameters were not much affected and all the parameters were passed and %RSD was within the limit. All the chromatogram are illustrated in Figure 22, 23, 24, 25, 26 and 27.

Figure 22. Flow minus Chromatogram of ABNE and NIPB.

Figure 23. Flow plus Chromatogram of ABNE and NIPB.

Figure 24. Melting Point minus chromatogram of ABNE and NIPB.

Figure 25. Melting Point Plus chromatogram of ABNE and NIPB.

Figure 26. Temp minus chromatogram of ABNE and NIPB.

Figure 27. Temp plus chromatogram of ABNE and NIPB.

CONCLUSION

The developed RP-HPLC method successfully enabled the simultaneous estimation of Abiraterone (ABNE) and Niraparib (NIPB) with clear and well-resolved retention times of 2.350 and 3.044 minutes, respectively. System suitability results confirmed excellent precision, with %RSD values of 0.2% for ABNE and 0.8% for NIPB. The method demonstrated high accuracy, as reflected by recovery percentages of 99.27% for ABNE and 99.97% for NIPB. Sensitivity was also established, with low LOD and LOQ values for both

drugs. The linearity of the method was validated through the regression equations $y = 36905x + 108959$ for ABNE and $y = 49978x + 5769$ for NIPB. Overall, the findings confirm that the proposed method is precise, accurate, sensitive, and highly suitable for routine quality control analysis of ABNE and NIPB in pharmaceutical formulations.

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